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Role of human action in the spread of honey bee pathogens

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Beekeepers: Part of the Solution or Part of the Problem?

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ABSTRACT The increased annual losses in European honey bee (*Apis mellifera*) colonies in North America and some other countries is usually attributed to a range of factors including pathogens, poor nutrition and insecticides. In this essay I will argue that the global trade in honeybees and migratory beekeeping practices within countries has enabled pathogens to spread quickly. Beekeepers' management strategies have also contributed to the spread of pathogens as well as the development of resistance to miticides and antibiotics, and exacerbated by hobby beekeepers. The opportunities for arresting honeybee declines rest as strongly with individual beekeepers as they do with the dynamics of disease.

KEY WORDS *Apis mellifera*, pathogens, global spread, beekeepers, management practices

The European honeybee, *Apis mellifera*, is globally important in crop pollination and for producing bee related substances ([Klein et al. 2007](#)). The health problems experienced by the European honeybee are well publicized and many people are increasingly aware of the high annual losses in honey bee colonies in North America and other countries ([Lee et al. 2015](#)). Honeybee mortality is often attributed to the mite *Varroa* ([Le Conte et al. 2010](#)). The honeybee, however, is afflicted with many pathogens and the causes of colony loss are complex ([Oldroyd 2007](#)). Many people interpret the spread of pathogens as a characteristic of the disease or pest in question ([Nadège et al. 2015](#)). However human activity contributes the most to the deterioration of honeybee health. Human actions affect honeybee conservation on several fronts: the global trade in honeybees and honeybee products has spread pathogens that might otherwise have remained localized ([Mutinelli 2011](#)); migratory beekeeping has spread pathogens within countries ([Crane 2000](#); [Lounsberry et al. 2010](#); [Gordon et al 2014](#)). Also, management practices and the lack of adherence to recognized Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies ([Caron et al. 2015](#)) as well as the role of hobby beekeepers in the spread of pathogens ([Traynor 2016](#)) demonstrate that human actions are contributing factors. While the environmental and economic implications of honeybee

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decline may be mitigated by changes in human behavior and governments in some instances share the responsibility for implementing these changes, I would argue that most change should occur in the behavior of individual keepers.

Varroa dispersal The mite *Varroa destructor* is regarded as the most important global threat to the European honeybee. The mite originated in north-east Asia where the Asian honeybee, *Apis cerana* is its natural host. The Asian honeybee and *Varroa* have co-evolved and successfully co-exist ([Rosencranz et al. 2009](#)). Eastern Russia was opened to imports of European honeybee colonies in 1905. From there they were transported to north-east Asia where *Varroa* and the European honeybee came into contact ([Oldroyd 1999](#)).

Varroa is believed to have jumped species from its natural host, the Asian honeybee, to the European honeybee twice in the 1950s ([Rosencranz et al. 2009](#)). As a result there are believed to be two haplotypes of *Varroa destructor* afflicting the European honeybee ([de Guzman et al 1999](#); [Solignac et al 2005](#)). It is a sobering thought that the destruction caused globally by *Varroa destructor* originated from as few as two female mites jumping species.

Due to the large-scale movement of European honeybee colonies out of north-east Asia post 1950, *Varroa* was found on local populations of the European honeybee in the eastern region of the USSR, in Pakistan, Japan, China, Bulgaria, Paraguay, Germany, and U.K. The first record of *Varroa* in the United States dates from 1987 and in Germany from 1977 ([Crane 2000](#); [Rosencranz et al. 2009](#)). Both haplotypes infest North American honeybees which implies that the mite may have entered North America at least twice ([de Guzman et al. 1999](#)). Entry may have been through illegal importation of queens or honeybees from Europe or as hitchhikers or swarms in containers or vessels.

In New Zealand *Varroa* was detected in April 2000. The mite was concentrated around Auckland airport and may have entered the country by plane a few years earlier ([Stevenson 2005](#)). *Varroa destructor* mites hosted by *Apis mellifera* have not yet invaded Australia although it has, on several occasions, been found on ships in Australian waters or in Australian ports and been destroyed ([AHBIC 2016](#)). This suggests that over time it is likely that a *Varroa* haplotype able to infest European honeybees will enter Australia.

History of Human Factors in the Spread of Pathogens Modern intensive agriculture requires the large-scale movement of bee colonies for commercial pollination ([Scientific American 2013](#)). The colonies are often transported many thousands of kilometers over a few days. Of the 2.66 million

managed honeybee colonies in the U.S., 1.8 million were transported to the Central Valley of California in February 2016 to pollinate the almond crop. It is likely that these colonies spread mites, beetles, viruses and other pathogens between colonies involved in almond pollination ([Fries & Camazine 2001](#); [Nadège et al. 2015](#), [Goodwin et al. 2006](#); [Greatti et al. 1992](#)).

When *Varroa* was first detected in the U.S. in 1987 the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency authorized the use of the miticide tau-fluvalinate for control of the mite. By 1995 there was wide ranging resistance to tau-fluvalinate amongst the *Varroa* population. In 1999 a second miticide, Coumaphos, was approved for use in the U.S. ([Johnson et al. 2010](#)). *Varroa's* resistance to Coumaphos in the U.S. was detected as early as 2001 ([Elzen & Westerveldt 2002](#)) implying that beekeepers had been using it prior to its legal approval.

As resistance to the two approved miticides for *Varroa* developed, many beekeepers started applying tau-fluvalinate and Coumaphos in excess of their recommended doses. This accelerated the development of resistance in the mite population ([Lodesani & Costa 2005](#); [Johnson et al 2010](#); [Tian et al. 2012](#)).

Even before the U.S. Department of Agriculture, USDA, had approved Amitraz for use against *Varroa* in 2013, low concentrations of Amitraz were being detected in beeswax during USDA analysis ([Johnson et al. 2010](#)). This implied that some beekeepers were using Amitraz illegally to treat infested colonies. Before Amitraz was approved and appropriately packaged for use in a hive, beekeepers needed to find a method to apply it to their colonies. Beekeepers did this by soaking strips of plywood in Amitraz and leaving the strips in the hive, often for longer than necessary to keep varroa numbers under control ([Johnson et al 2010](#)). Beekeepers determined the effective dose for Amitraz by how fast mites were reduced in the colony, not by the possible build-up of resistance due to overuse of the miticide. This again was in violation of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) principles such as determining the appropriate dose of a miticide by hive inspections, minimizing the amount applied, and rotating miticides to minimize the risk of build-up of resistance ([Delaplane 2005](#)).

With the global spread of *Varroa* and its role in the transmission of viruses to honey bees ([Kuster et al. 2014](#)), multiple infections of which have been shown to correlate with colony losses or poor colony health, and the increase in resistance to miticides, honeybee colony losses in North America and some other countries have increased dramatically ([Oldroyd 2007](#)). The U.S. continues to have the highest annual colony losses, 44% during 2015-2016 ([Beeinformed 2016](#)). In Europe losses are

much lower and varied from 29.3% in U.K. to 5.6% in Italy during 2012-2013, with a trend towards lower colony losses as latitude decreased ([EU 2016a](#)).

Pathogens Other than *Varroa* More than twenty viruses infect honeybees ([Sumpter & Martin 2004](#)), some of which are spread by *Varroa*. Deformed Wing Virus (DWV), the most lethal virus associated with *Varroa*, was initially detected in honey bees in Japan in the early 1980s ([Berényi O et al. 2007](#)) and has since spread globally driven by the trade and movement of the honeybee ([Wilfert et al. 2016](#)).

American Foul Brood, AFB, caused by the bacterium *Paenibacillus larvae*, was the most serious infection of honeybees globally prior to *Varroa* ([White 1906](#)). In Europe beekeepers are usually legally required to keep AFB in check by destroying an infected colony and burning the hive. In New Zealand, where destroying the hive and colony are strictly enforced, the incidence of AFB between 1998 and today has fluctuated between 0.31% and 0.26% ([AFB 2016](#)).

In the U.S. and Canada many beekeepers treat their colonies prophylactically with the antibiotics Tetracycline or Tylosin at the start of every winter ([Elzen & Westerveldt 2002](#); [Blackston 2009](#); [Nasr 2014](#)). Tylosin was introduced to replace Tetracycline since there is now widespread resistance to Tetracycline by AFB in the U.S. ([Evans 2003](#), [Tian et al 2012](#)). The use of Tetracycline is ineffective at eradicating AFB as spores are unaffected by the antibiotic and can persist for decades in honey, comb and on hive material.

AFB is occasionally encountered in managed colonies partly because beekeepers spread the disease on dirty tools and by reusing infected hive parts ([Goodwin 2006](#)). AFB is much less common in feral colonies ([Goodwin et al 1994](#)), perhaps due to the much larger distance between feral nests or because AFB may have difficulty spreading unaided.

The fungal disease chalkbrood, *Ascosphaera apis*, was mainly found in Europe until the mid-20th century ([Aronstein & Murray 2010](#)). The first major report of spread was to New Zealand in 1952. Later it was found in Argentina, Turkey and in Utah in the U.S. (in 1965) from where it quickly spread to California and other states. Chalkbrood was reported in Australia in 1993 and quickly spread to all states ([Hornitzky 2001](#)). The U.S. and Australia have migratory beekeeping cultures which allow pathogens to disperse quickly ([Gordon et al. 2014](#)).

Tracheal mite, *Acarapis woodi*, ([COLOSS 2016](#)) has been reported on every continent except Australia and New Zealand. In the U.S. it was first found in Texas in 1984. Thereafter tracheal mite spread to all of the states facilitated by commercial beekeepers transporting bees for pollination and

from the sale of mite-infested package bees. Initially the serious economic impact of tracheal mites in the U.S. was not anticipated due to conflicting reports from Europe. It soon became evident that the mite was having a severe detrimental effect on beekeeping in the U.S. and was spreading faster than anticipated. It is apparent that the mite found an extremely susceptible honey bee host in the U.S. ([USDA 2016](#)).

[Bailey \(1964\)](#) states that beekeepers in the U.K. did not understand the disastrous effects of their own actions in the spread of tracheal mite in the earlier part of the last century, including experimental treatments, moving bees and especially transferring bees from skeps to moveable-frame hives.

Small Hive Beetle, *Aethina tumida* ([Neumann et al 2016](#)) was not known outside sub-Saharan Africa before 1996. Small Hive Beetle was subsequently found in North America in (1996), Australia (2001) and Calabria, Italy (2014) ([Lounsberry et al. 2010](#); [EU 2016b](#)). Due to the large distances between sub-Saharan Africa and North America, Australia and Italy, human assistance can be assumed for the global spread of this pest.

The natural host of the microsporidian fungus *Nosema cerana* is the Asian honeybee, *A. cerana*. It is believed to have jumped species from the Asian honeybee to the European honeybee in the 1990s ([Klee et al. 2007](#)). *N. cerana* is now found infecting European honeybees globally and is believed to be a significant contributor to colony losses in Europe ([Higes et al. 2008](#)). Again, for this microsporidian to have spread globally so rapidly human assistance must be assumed.

Hobby beekeepers Many hobby beekeepers do not have either the skills or the interest to inspect and manage colonies for disease and are frequently responsible for other problems such as uncontrolled swarming ([ABC Rural 2016](#), [Guardian 2016](#)). Urban colonies, most of which are owned by hobby beekeepers, are three times more likely to die than colonies located in rural areas ([Youngsteadt et al. 2015](#)). In *varroa* infected colonies, the death of a colony results in the spread of mites by the remaining workers moving to other hives, this activity is often called a '*varroa bomb*' ([Connor 2015](#)). Although this finding applies to both feral and managed colonies, it shows that urban hobby beekeepers, who comprise the majority of beekeepers, albeit with a small number of hives, are faced with a far wider range of problems than their rural counterparts.

In Australia both the total number of hives and professional beekeepers decreased between 2006 and 2014 ([Crooks 2008](#); [BeeAware 2016](#)). During the same period the number of hives managed by hobbyists with < 50 hives increased, as did the percentage of total beekeepers that were hobbyists.

Data for the U.S. is difficult to obtain although there appears to be a high turn-over of hobby beekeepers possibly caused by the difficulty of managing diseased colonies.

60% of hobby beekeepers in the U.S. do not monitor or treat for *Varroa* while commercially managed colonies generally have lower levels of *Varroa* ([Traynor et al. 2016](#)). Untreated colonies rapidly collapse and provide opportunities for *Varroa* to disperse to other colonies. Beekeepers who are working to manage *Varroa* are often stymied by a minority of beekeepers who do not manage pests and diseases effectively. [Traynor et al. \(2106\)](#) noted, however, that while the incidence of *Varroa* was greater in colonies managed by hobbyists, the incidence of *Nosema* was greater in hives managed by commercial migratory beekeepers. In the U.S. hobby beekeepers' self-identified manageable factors such as starvation or weak colonies in the autumn as the main causes of over-winter colony losses. Commercial beekeepers generally self-identified non-manageable factors such as queen failure or pesticides for over-winter colony losses ([Steinhauer et al. 2014](#)).

An incursion of an exotic pathogen into a country is more likely to occur at a shipping port or an airport. These facilities are typically built near urban areas where the majority of beekeepers are hobbyists who often do not adequately monitor for pests and diseases. These factors make it possible for pathogen to spread widely into the local honeybee population before being detected.

Discussion

Humans have played a major role in the global distribution of honey bees (*Apis mellifera*) and their associated pathogens, with the diverse problems that afflict honeybees globally being closely related to human activity. In the management of the honeybee we must take urgent steps to:

1. further regulate the global transport of honeybees and bee products with enhanced pathogen testing so that pests and diseases are not inadvertently transmitted
2. regulate movement within countries such as the U.S. and Australia where migratory beekeeping is an important part of both commercial pollination and honey production. Movement of colonies should only be allowed if the risk of pathogen spread from possibly infected or infested colonies is understood and accepted by both governments, beekeepers and the agricultural industry
3. encourage people who manage honeybees, both commercially and hobbyists, to use proven Integrated Pest Management (IPM) techniques to control pathogens

4. ensure that hobby beekeepers are educated to understand their responsibilities and to monitor and treat for pathogens in their colonies
5. beekeeping education specialists to present courses for hobbyists and experienced beekeepers. Possibly making attendance at a pathogen management course each year a requirement for registration as a beekeeper
6. establish hobby beekeeper support networks, funded by beekeeping associations and/or government, or staffed by volunteers, that are skilled in the diagnoses and treatment of honey bee pathogens. These networks will aid hobby beekeepers in the appropriate management of their colonies and provide advice on suitable IPM techniques.

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References

- ABC Rural. 2016.** Beekeeping as a hobby all the buzz in suburban backyards. Australian Broadcasting Corporation. Australia. Available from (<http://www.abc.net.au/news/2016-01-07/tch-domestic-beekeeping-increasingly-popular/7073000>).
- AFB 2016.** Elimination of American Foulbrood (AFB) Disease in New Zealand. National American Foulbrood Pest Management Plan. New Zealand. Available from (<http://www.afb.org.nz/incidence>).
- AHBIC. 2016.** Australian Honeybee Industry Council. Australia. Available from (<http://honeybee.org.au/apis-cerana-in-townsville/>).
- Aronstein KA, Murray KD. 2010.** Chalkbrood disease in honey bees. *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology* 103. S20–S29.

- Bailey L. 1964.** The Isle of Wight Disease: the origin and significance of the myth. *Bee World*. 45:32-37.
- BeeAware. 2016.** Plant Health Australia. Canberra, Australia. Available from (<http://beeaware.org.au/industry/>).
- Beeinformed 2016.** Nation's Beekeepers Lost 44 Percent of Bees in 2015-16. *Bee Informed Partnership*. USA. Available from (<https://beeinformed.org/2016/05/10/nations-beekeepers-lost-44-percent-of-bees-in-2015-16/>).
- Berényi O, Bakonyi T, Derakhshifar I, Köglberger H, Topolska G, Ritter W, Pechhacker H, Nowotny N. 2007.** Phylogenetic Analysis of Deformed Wing Virus Genotypes from Diverse Geographic Origins Indicates Recent Global Distribution of the Virus. *Appl Environ Microbiol*. 73. 3605-3611.
- Blackston H. 2009.** *Beekeeping for Dummies*. p155, p199.
- Caron D, Epstein D, Hansen G, Rogers D, Sears R, Steeger T. 2015.** *Tools for Varroa Management: healthy bees . healthy people . healthy planet*. Honey Bee Health Coalition. USA. Available from (<http://honeybeehealthcoalition.org/varroa/>).
- Chauzat MP, Carpentier P, Martel AC, Bougeard S, Cougoule N, Porta P, Lachaize J, Madec F, Aubert M, Faucon JP. 2009.** Influence of pesticide residues on honeybee. (Hymenoptera: Apidae) colony health in France. *Environmental Entomology*. 38:514-523.
- COLOSS 2016.** *Tracheal Mite Acarapis woodi (Rennie)*. BEEBOOK. Swiss Bee Research Centre. Switzerland. Available from (<http://www.coloss.org/beebook/II/tracheal>).
- Connor L. 2015.** Varroa Control Past and Future. *American Bee Journal*. September 2015.
- Crane E. 2000.** Prevention and Treatment of Diseases and Pests of Honey Bees: The world picture. *New Zealand Beekeeper* 10:5-8.
- Crooks S. 2008.** Australian Honeybee Industry Survey 2006-07. Rural Industries Research and Development Corporation. Canberra. Australia. Publication No. 08/170. Available from (<https://rirdc.infoservices.com.au/downloads/08-170>).
- de Guzman L, Rinderer TE, Stelza JA. 1999.** Occurrence of two genotypes of *Varroa jacobsoni* Oud. in North America. *Apidologie*. 30:31-36.
- de Mirander JR, Gautier L, Ribiere M, Chen YP. 2012.** Honey Bee Viruses and Their Effect on Bee and Colony Health. Pages 71-102 in D. Sammataro and JA Yoder editors. *Honey Bee Colony Health, Challenges and Sustainable Solutions*. CRC Press, USA.

- Delaplane KS, Berry JA, Skinner JA, Parkman JP, Hood WM. 2005.** Integrated pest management against varroa destructor reduces colony mite levels and delays treatment threshold. *Journal of Apicultural Research*. 44:157-162.
- Elzen PJ, Westerveldt D. 2002.** Detection of coumaphos resistance in Varroa destructor in Florida. *American Bee Journal*. 142:291-292.
- EU 2016a.** Study on honeybee colony mortality. European Commission. Available from (http://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/bees/study_on_mortality/index_en.htm).
- EU 2016b.** Small hive beetle outbreaks. European Commission. Available from (http://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/bees/small_hive_beetle_outbreaks/index_en.htm).
- Evans J. 2003.** Diverse origins of tetracycline resistance in the honeybee bacterial pathogen *Paenibacillus* larvae. *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology*. 83:45-60.
- Fries I, Camazine S. 2001.** Implications of horizontal and vertical pathogen transmission for honeybee epidemiology. *Apidologie*. 32:199-214.
- Goodwin RM, Houten AT, Perry JH. 1994.** Incidence of American foulbrood infections in feral honeybee colonies in New Zealand. *New Zealand Journal of Zoology*. 21:285-287.
- Goodwin RM. 2006.** Elimination of American Foulbrood Disease without the use of Drugs. A Practical Manual for Beekeepers. National Beekeepers' Association of New Zealand.
- Goodwin RM, Taylor MA, McBrydie HM. 2006.** Drift of Varroa destructor infested worker honey bees to neighbouring colonies. *J. Apic. Res.* 45: 155-56
- Gordon R, Bresolin-Schott N, East IJ. 2014.** Nomadic beekeeper movements create the potential for widespread disease in the honeybee industry. *Australian Veterinary Journal*. 92:283-290.
- Greatti M, Milani N, Nazzi F. 1992.** Reinfestation of an acaricide-treated apiary by Varroa jacobsoni Oud. *Exp. Appl. Acarol.* 16: 279-86
- Guardian. 2016.** Guardian Newspapers, UK. Available from (www.theguardian.com/environment/2015/may/14/yes-bad-beekeeping-is-to-blame-for-unwanted-urban-swarms).
- Higes M, Martin-Hernandez R, Botias C, Bailón EG, González-Porto AV, Barrios L, del Nozal MJ, Bernal JL, Jiménez JJ, Palencia PG, Meana A. 2008.** How natural infection by *Nosema ceranae* causes honeybee colony collapse. *Environmental Microbiology*. 10:2659-2669.

- Hornitzky M. 2001.** Literature Review of Chalk Brood a Fungal disease. Rural Industries Research and Development Corporation, Canberra, Australia. Available from: (<https://rirdc.infoservices.com.au/downloads/01-150>).
- Johnson RM, Ellis MD, Mullin CA, Frazier M. 2010.** Pesticides and honeybee toxicity – USA. *Apidologie*. 41:312-331.
- Klee J, Besana AM, Genersch E, Gisder S, Nanetti A, Tam DQ, Chinh TX, Puerta F, Ruz JM, Kryger P, Message D, Hatjina F, Korpela S, Fries I, Paxton RJ. 2007.** Widespread dispersal of the microsporidian *Nosema ceranae*, an emergent pathogen of the western honeybee, *Apis mellifera*. *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology*. 96:1-10.
- Klein et al. 2007. Klein A-M, Vaissière BE, Cane JH, Steffan-D I, Cunningham SA, Kremen C, Tscharntke T. 2007.** Importance of pollinators in changing landscapes for world crops. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B, Biological Science*. 274:303-313.
- Kuster et al. 2014. Kuster RD, Boncristiani HF, Rueppell O. 2014.** Immunogene and viral transcript dynamics during parasitic *Varroa destructor* mite infection of developing honey bee (*Apis mellifera*) pupae. *J. Exp. Biol*. 217: 1710-1718
- Le Conte Y, Ellis M, Ritter M. 2010.** *Varroa* mites and honeybee health: can *Varroa* explain part of the colony losses? *Apidologie*. 41:353-363.
- Lee KV, Steinhauer N, Rennich K, Wilson ME, Tarpy DR, Caron DM, Rose R, Delaplane KS, Baylis K, Lengerich EJ, Pettis J, Skinner JA, Wilkes JT, Sagili R, vanEngelsdorp D. 2015.** A national survey of managed honeybee 2013–2014 annual colony losses in the USA. *Apidologie*. 46:292-305.
- Lodesani M, Costa M. 2005.** Limits of chemotherapy in beekeeping: Development of resistance and the problem of residues. *Bee World*. 86:102–109.
- Lounsberry Z, Spiewoks S, Pernal SF, Sonstegard TS, Hood WM, Pettis J, Neumann P, Evans JD. 2010.** Worldwide Diaspora of *Aethina tumida* (Coleoptera: Nitidulidae), a Nest Parasite of Honeybees. *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*. 103:671-677.
- Mutinelli F. 2011.** The spread of pathogens through trade in honeybees and their products (including queen bees and semen): overview and recent developments. *Scientific and Technical Review of the Office International des Epizooties (Paris)*. 30:257-271.

- Nadège F, Natsopoulou ME, Frey E, Rosenkranz P, Paxton RJ, Moritz A. 2015.** Parasites and Pathogens of the Honeybee (*Apis mellifera*) and Their Influence on Inter-Colonial Transmission. PLOS one. e0140337. [doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0140337](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0140337).
- Nasr 2014.** Nasr M. Recommendations for Management of Honeybee Diseases and Pests in Alberta 2014-2015.
([www1.agric.gov.ab.ca/\\$Department/deptdwww1.agric.gov.ab.ca/\\$Department/deptdocs.nsf/all/prm13239/\\$FILE/2014-recommendations.pdf](http://www1.agric.gov.ab.ca/$Department/deptdwww1.agric.gov.ab.ca/$Department/deptdocs.nsf/all/prm13239/$FILE/2014-recommendations.pdf);
[prmfocs.nsf/all/prm13239/\\$FILE/2014-recommendations.pdf](http://prmfocs.nsf/all/prm13239/$FILE/2014-recommendations.pdf)).
- Neumann P, Pettis JS, Schäfer MO. 2016.** Quo vadis *Aethina tumida*? Biology and control of small hive beetles. *Apidologie*. 47: 427–466.
- Oldroyd BP. 1999.** Coevolution while you wait: *Varroa jacobsoni*, a new parasite of western honeybee. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*. 14:312-315.
- Oldroyd BP. 2007.** What's Killing American Honeybees? PLOS Biology. e168. [doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.0050168](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.0050168).
- Rosenkranz P, Aumeier P, Ziegelmann B. 2009.** Biology and control of *Varroa destructor*. *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology*. 103: S96-S119.
- Scientific American, 2013.** The Mind-Boggling Math of Migratory Beekeeping. *Scientific American Magazine*, USA. Available from
(<http://www.scientificamerican.com/article/migratory-beekeeping-mind-boggling-math/>).
- Solignac M, Cornuet J-M, Vautrin D, Le Conte Y, Anderson D, Evans J, Cros-Arteil S, Navajas M. 2005.** The invasive Korea and Japan types of *Varroa destructor*, ectoparasitic mites of the Western honeybee (*Apis mellifera*), are two partly isolated clones. *Proc. R. Soc. B* 272, 411–419. [doi:10.1098/rspb.2004.2853](https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2004.2853).
- Steinhauer NA et al. 2014.** A national survey of managed honey bee 2012-2013 annual colony losses in the USA: results from the Bee Informed Partnership. *Journal of Apicultural Research* 53:1-18.
- Stevenson MA, Bernard H, Bolger P, Morris RS. 2005.** Spatial epidemiology of the Asian honeybee mite (*Varroa destructor*) in the North Island of New Zealand. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*. 71:241-252.
- Sumpter DJT, Martin SJ. 2004.** The dynamics of virus epidemics in *Varroa*-infested honeybee colonies. *Journal of Animal Ecology*. 73:51-63.

- Tan B, Fadhil NHJ, Powell JE, Kwong WK, Moran NA. 2012.** Long-Term Exposure to Antibiotics Has Caused Accumulation of Resistance Determinants in the Gut Microbiota of Honeybees. *mBio*. 3 (6): e00377-12
- Tian B, Fadhil NH, Powell JE, Kwong WK, and Moran NA. 2012.** Long-Term Exposure to Antibiotics Has Caused Accumulation of Resistance Determinants in the Gut Microbiota of Honeybees. *mBio*. 3(6): e00377-12
- Traynor KS, Rennich K, Forsgren E, Rose R, Pettis J, Kunkel G, Madella S, Evans J, Lopez D, vanEngelsdorp D. 2016.** Multiyear survey targeting disease incidence in US honey bees. *Apidologie*. 47: 325-347. [doi:10.1007/s13592-016-0431-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13592-016-0431-0).
- USDA. 2016.** (<https://www.ars.usda.gov/northeast-area/beltsville-md/beltsville-agricultural-research-center/bee-research-laboratory/docs/tracheal-mite/>).
- White GF. 1906.** The bacteria of the apiary with special reference to bee disease. US Department of Agriculture, Bureau of Entomology, Technical Series, No. 14 (1906), 50 pp.
- Wilfert et al. 2016.** Deformed wing virus is a recent global epidemic in honeybees driven by Varroa mites. *Science*. 6273: 594-597.
- Youngsteadt E, Appler RH, López-Urbe MM, Tarpy DR, Frank SD. 2015.** Urbanization Increases Pathogen Pressure on Feral and Managed Honeybees. *PLOS one*. e0142031. [doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0142031](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0142031).